

IPBES VA Chapter 4 - Literature & case study review on outcomes in payments for ecosystem services / compensation for ecosystem services (PES/CES) programmes / IPBES values assessment 4.7

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Description

The IPBES Scoping document for the values assessment highlights the need to assess the types of values of nature and valuation practices that have (or have not) been incorporated into decision-making, the challenges that have hindered the incorporation of diverse conceptualizations of values of nature in a range of decision and policy-making contexts, and the implications for decision outcomes. To this end, we conducted a literature and case-study review to examine how values are articulated by diverse stakeholders through payments for ecosystem services / compensation for ecosystem services (PES/CES) programs, including REDD+, to determine (1) what factors have been shown to influence PES outcomes, and by what mechanisms; and (2) how these factors relate to (mis)alignments among local and program values, institutions, and knowledge systems, in order to (3) assess the potential for plural valuation to enhance PES outcomes. We then augment this review with deep case studies that further examine how misalignments arise in PES and how they influence outcomes, and to identify (4) what value articulation processes are most effective at aligning local values, institutions, and knowledge systems with PES design and implementation; and (5) what contextual factors support/undermine these efforts.

Process overview

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Protocol:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Literature review of review papers
- **Search language:** English
- **Search Date:** 22 April 2020 and 26 October 2020 (yielded 11 additional papers)
- **Search engine:** Web of Science
- **Search terms:**

TS=("payment* for ecosystem services" OR "payment* for watershed services" OR "investment* in watershed services" OR "water fund*" OR "payment* for environmental services" OR "investment* in environmental services" OR "investment* in ecosystem services" OR "investment* in ecological services" OR "payment* for ecological services" OR REDD OR REDD+) AND TS = ("outcome*" OR "impact*" OR "leakage" OR "biodiversity" OR "justice" OR "equity")
Refined by: "review"
- **Sample extracted:** 275 review papers on outcomes in PES/CES and REDD+

Treatment applied: Review papers were then screened based on title and abstract, and tagged according to themes of relevance to the section and geographical scope, with the most relevant papers given a “starred” tag (e.g. “PES outcomes;” “PES review;” “PES values;” “PES in [region/country];” “PES starred”). We then prioritised the most relevant papers based on these tags, with “PES starred,” “PES review,” and “PES outcomes” given the highest priority. This prioritisation yielded 40 starred review papers of highest priority (starred papers that were not reviews were not coded in the review, but were read as background to inform the analysis). We prioritised review papers that covered impacts of programs in more than one country.

- **Sample extracted (A):** 167 relevant papers, (40 of highest priority)
- **Fields (A):**
 - Priority
 - Citation
 - PES starred
 - PES review
 - PES values + outcomes
 - PES outcomes
 - PES values
 - PES mismatch
 - PES participation
 - PES justice
 - PES knowledge
 - PES politics
 - PES power
 - PES leakage
 - PES crowding in/out
 - PES biodiversity
 - PES motivation
 - PES participatory
- **Location and format of the data (A):** IPBES_VA_4.7_2020_(A).csv

Treatment applied: We adapted the framework from Bayrak and Marafa (2016) to categorise impacts in five dimensions: institutional, livelihood, socio-cultural, target ecosystem services, and other environmental outcomes. These outcome categories were later harmonised with the categories identified for use across the section.

We used an emergent coding approach to identify influencing factors, the mechanisms by which they influence various outcomes, and the feedbacks among them. We then grouped these factors into broad categories, identifying factors related to the (mis)alignment between PES design/implementation and participant values, knowledge systems, and institutions. We focused on these areas with the understanding that values are embedded in and articulated through knowledge systems and institutions. Our focus on (mis)alignments differs from other reviews that have correlated various design or contextual features with PES success (Calvet-Mir et al. 2015; Boerner et al. 2017) by highlighting the interactions among program design and contextual elements as well as the mechanisms by which these influence outcomes. Illustrative examples of influencing factors, outcomes, and feedbacks appear in **(B)**.

We conducted a case-study review (deep cases) to show:

- 1) the process by which certain values and ways of knowing influence PES problematization,¹ design, implementation, and outcomes assessment, highlighting the role of power relations;
- 2) how multiple dimensions of justice influence outcomes; and
- 3) how, and at what stages, inclusion of diverse values may enhance justice and facilitate alignment among program design and local values, knowledge, and institutions.

The value of this approach lies in a deep assessment of the literature on a diversity of PES programs to describe the process from PES design, through implementation, to outcomes, in order to understand how values are articulated through PES and how misalignments in relation to values, institutions, and knowledge systems arise.

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Review of case studies
- **Contribution language:** English
- **Selection criteria:** A set of case studies on PES/CES were selected based on the following criteria, subject to the availability of the contributing-authors drafting these cases:
 - Availability of research addressing:
 - Design and implementation process:
 - Program design and participation (procedural)
 - Value articulation process (procedural/recognition)
 - Benefit distribution (distributive)
 - Cost distribution (distributive)
 - For all of these: esp. studies addressing participants' motivations and perception of impacts
 - Quality of life impacts
 - Impacts of benefits on participants (objective measures of e.g. income, wealth, or well-being impacts) AND/OR
 - Participants' perceptions of impacts (subjective accounts)
 - Evidence of value crowding
 - Environmental impacts
 - Environmental outcomes, including monitoring and measures of effectiveness
 - Desirable but not essential: stakeholders' perceptions of environmental impacts; data on off-site impacts/leakage; biodiversity impacts
 - Mix of region, governance structure and scale, and biophysical context.

Case studies have been compiled by experts with long-term in-depth research experience in their focus program. Document (C) presents the guiding questions sent to contributing authors for the development of the case studies.

¹ By 'problematization,' we mean the process of defining the environmental problem to be addressed, and the choice of PES as solution.

- **Sample extracted (D):** 8 case studies
 - **Costa Rica, National Payments for Ecosystem Services (Pagos por Servicios Ambientales)** CA: Dr. David Lansing. Established 1997. One of the most long-standing and well-researched national PES programs, encompassing reforestation and forest protection to promote carbon sequestration, hydrological services, biodiversity, and scenic beauty. Administered by the National Forest Financing Fund, a quasi-state institution funded by gasoline taxes, water tariffs, and multilateral agency loans. Monetary payments according to 10 different payment modalities (ranging from 3-13 modalities through the life of the program). The program is highly popular, while assessments of its environmental effectiveness vary widely.
 - **Mexico, National PES and related programs.** CAs: Dr. Elizabeth Shapiro-Garza and Dr. Santiago Izquierdo Tort. A policy mix encompassing four programs, established 2003 (National PES), 2006 (REDD+ Readiness), 2008 (Local Mechanisms for PES through Matching Funds), and 2010 (Biodiversity Heritage Fund), respectively. Administered by the federal forestry agency, Comisión Nacional Forestal. Monetary payments. The program is popular and has evolved over time in response to popular mobilization demanding greater recognition of rural values and stewardship.
 - **China, Sloping Lands Conversion Program (also known as Grain for Green).** CA: Dr. Jun He. Established 1999. The largest PES program globally, currently implemented in 25 provinces and enrolling over 120 million households. Goals are to increase forest cover and prevent soil erosion through conversion of marginal agricultural land into forest, while supporting transition to non-farm rural livelihoods. Administered by the national government, with varying degrees of decentralization and local decision-making in implementation. In-kind and monetary compensation.
 - **Australia: Indigenous savanna burning for carbon abatement and fire management.** CA: Dr. Sue Jackson. Savanna burning based on an integration of Indigenous and non-Indigenous practices was granted eligibility as a carbon abatement tool under Australia's Emissions Reduction Fund in 2015, following extensive work by Indigenous organizations, researchers, and land management agencies, and a model program initiated in 2006. One-third of the 78 savanna burning projects nationally are administered by Indigenous ranger groups. Credits are purchased by the Australian government in the national single-buyer carbon market, and are also eligible for sale under the Kyoto Protocol. Socio-cultural benefits of improved savanna management, including access to traditional sites, are major motivators of program participation.
 - **Pastures, Conservation and Climate Action (PCCA), Mongolia.** CA: Caroline Upton. Co-designed PES, developed in partnership with participating herder communities, established in 2015 in three sites covering 78,000 hectares and 130 herding households. The program promotes improvement of herding practices for soil carbon sequestration, biodiversity conservation, and habitat. Credits are certified under the Plan Vivo Standard mandating livelihood and wellbeing benefits to participants, and herders' participation in governance. Site-specific management plans and targets were co-developed with herder groups, with 90% participation of group membership across the three sites. 70% of funds from carbon credit sales are administered to participating communities.
 - **REDD+ in Cross River, Nigeria.** CAs: Adeniyi Asiyambi and Usman Isyaku. Nigeria's national REDD+ program went into force in 2011, with groundwork dating back to 2008. Demonstration activities were pursued in Cross River State, an area of high biodiversity importance, alongside national policy rollout. In the context of conflicting

customary and formal land rights, REDD+ has been implemented in combination with policies that criminalized deforestation, with significant negative impacts on local livelihoods and communities. Shortfalls in the expected payments and benefits of REDD+, combined with these costs, has caused resistance to and resentment of the program among some affected communities.

- **Fund for Water Protection (Fondo para la protección del agua, FONAG), Ecuador.** CAs: Leah Bremer and Marta Echavarría. FONAG is a trust fund established in 2000 by The Nature Conservancy and Quito's water utility, EPMAPS (Empresa Pública Metropolitana de Agua Potable y Saneamiento de Quito), to finance conservation activities in biodiverse Andean ecosystems important for the water supply of the city of Quito. FONAG covers four primary focal areas: 1) water management; 2) sustainable water conservation areas; 3) restoration and recuperation of vegetation and soils in areas of hydrologic importance; and 4) environmental education. Compensation to participants is provided through in-kind support of productive projects, and the program has evolved to integrate greater community involvement in implementation over time. FONAG has served as a model for many water funds in Latin America and beyond.
- **Watershared agreements (Acuerdos Recíprocos por Agua) in Bolivia.** CA: Nigel Asquith. Watershared Agreements (Acuerdos Recíprocos por Agua in Spanish) encompass a variety of locally-specific arrangements to enable support, by downstream water users, of conservation and rural development activities for upstream populations. They have been adopted in 58 municipalities in Bolivia, involving a variety of institutional actors, including several local NGOs and municipalities. Watershared programs are negotiated between upstream and downstream participants at the local level, to provide upstream landowners with in-kind material support for economic alternatives – such as fruit trees, irrigation pipes and beehives – in exchange for forest conservation.
- **Location and format of the data (D):** IPBES_VA_4.7_2020_(D).pdf

Treatment applied: We assessed what kinds of values were prioritised, for what stakeholders, at four stages of the PES process – problematization, program design, implementation, and monitoring/assessment – and the role of knowledge and power relations in elevating some values over others at each of these stages. By 'problematization,' we mean the definition of the environmental problem to be addressed, and the choice of PES as solution. We assessed the process of decision-making and the role of various stakeholders at international, domestic, and local scales. Experts also assessed available literature on participant motivations in order to illuminate mismatches between incentive schemes and participant values.

We used a 3-point scale to score each program according to how effectively it addressed multiple dimensions of justice at the problematization, design, and implementation stages. These scores provide a tool to track how (mis)alignments among values, institutions, and knowledge systems relate to multiple dimensions of justice, where these (mis)alignments occur, how they affect program sustainability and outcomes, and how they may evolve within a given program over time. They also assist in identifying data gaps. *They do not in themselves provide conclusive judgement on justice or injustice in a given instance.* These scores were interpreted qualitatively to inform the holistic case analysis. Explanations of the criteria used to assess these scores are available in **(R1)**.

Definition of files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_VA_4.7_2020_(A)	csv	49 KB	List of 167 relevant papers, including 40 of highest priority
B	IPBES_VA_4.7_2020_(B)	pdf	123 KB	Illustrative examples of influencing factors, outcomes, and feedbacks
C	IPBES_VA_4.7_2020_(C)	pdf	185 KB	Guiding questions for drafting the case studies
D	IPBES_VA_4.7_2020_(D)	pdf	1 MB	Case studies on PES/CES prepared by contributing authors
R1	IPBES_VA_4.7_2020_(R1)	pdf	139 KB	Explanations of the criteria used to assess the 3-point scale to score PES case studies